

The Indefinite Integral of the Factorial Function

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ABSTRACT. We prove that the indefinite integral of a factorial function, specifically $x!$ ($\int x! dx$) exists an approximate result as a multivariable function which is $\frac{x!x}{x \ln x - y \ln y + \frac{y+3}{2}}$.

1. Introduction

The factorial function $x!$ can be notated as $\prod_{n=1}^x n$ or as a continuous function $\Gamma(x + 1) = x\Gamma(x)$. The gamma function ($\Gamma(x) = (x - 1)!$) can be notated in integral form which is $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-t} t^{x-1} dt$ or $\int_0^1 \ln^n(x) dx$. The derivative of $x!$ is also really important for the proof of the indefinite integral for u-substitution. The derivative of $x!$ is $x!\Psi(x + 1)$ where $\Psi(x)$ is the digamma function which is a definition with an integral form of $\int_0^{\infty} e^{-t} - \frac{1}{1-t^x} dt$ and an approximate form of $\ln(x) - \frac{1}{2x}$.

2. The Proof

We start with the integral of $x!$ and then you would turn it to $x\Gamma(x)$ then use the IBP method where $u = \Gamma(x)$ and $dv = x$:

$$\int x! dx = \int x\Gamma(x) dx$$

$$\int x\Gamma(x) dx = \frac{x^2\Gamma(x)}{2} - \int \frac{x^2\Gamma'(x)}{2} dx$$

$$\int x\Gamma(x) dx = \frac{x^2\Gamma(x)}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \int x^2\Gamma'(x) dx$$

Then we change $\Gamma'(x)$ to $\Gamma(x)\Psi(x)$ and factorize it (and also change the first $x\Gamma(x)$ to $x!$):

$$\int x! dx = \frac{x^2\Gamma(x)}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \int x^2\Gamma(x)\Psi(x) dx$$

$$\int x! dx = \frac{x^2\Gamma(x)}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \int (x\Gamma(x))(x\Psi(x)) dx$$

We then approximate $\Psi(x)$ to its approximate form which is $\ln(x) + \frac{1}{2x}$:

$$\int x! dx = \frac{x^2\Gamma(x)}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \int (x\Gamma(x))(x(\ln(x) + \frac{1}{2x})) dx$$

$$\int x! dx = \frac{x^2\Gamma(x)}{2} - \frac{1}{2}\int (x\Gamma(x))(x\ln(x) + \frac{1}{2}) dx$$

$$\int x! dx = \frac{x^2\Gamma(x)}{2} - \frac{1}{2}\int x^2\ln(x)\Gamma(x) + \frac{1}{2}x\Gamma(x) dx$$

$$\int x! dx = \frac{x^2\Gamma(x)}{2} - \frac{1}{2}\int x^2\ln(x)\Gamma(x) dx + \frac{1}{4}\int x\Gamma(x) dx$$

$$\int x! dx = \frac{x^2\Gamma(x)}{2} - \frac{1}{2}\int x^2\ln(x)\Gamma(x) dx + \frac{1}{4}\int x! dx$$

And based on the laws of algebra, you can subtract the $\frac{1}{4}\int x! dx$ on both sides:

$$\frac{3}{4}\int x! dx = \frac{x^2\Gamma(x)}{2} - \frac{1}{2}\int x^2\ln(x)\Gamma(x) dx$$

And now we factorize the $x^2\ln(x)\Gamma(x)$ to $(x\ln(x))(x\Gamma(x))$ and use IBP on the factorized function:

$$\frac{3}{4}\int x! dx = \frac{x^2\Gamma(x)}{2} - \frac{1}{2}\int (x\ln(x))(x\Gamma(x)) dx$$

$$\frac{3}{4}\int x! dx = \frac{x^2\Gamma(x)}{2} - \frac{1}{2}(x\ln(x)\int x\Gamma(x) dx - \int \ln(x)\int x\Gamma(x) dx - \int x\Gamma(x) dx dx)$$

$$\frac{3}{2}\int x! dx = x^2\Gamma(x) - (x\ln(x)\int x\Gamma(x) dx - \int \ln(x)\int x\Gamma(x) dx dx - \int \int x\Gamma(x) dx dx)$$

$$\frac{3}{2}\int x! dx = x^2\Gamma(x) - x\ln(x)\int x\Gamma(x) dx + \int \ln(x)\int x\Gamma(x) dx dx + \int \int x\Gamma(x) dx dx$$

Then we turn one of the functions in the integral to a function with variable y (The y is its own variable and at the end we are not going to change y back to x, there will be an explanation for y at the end):

$$\frac{3}{2}\int x! dx = x^2\Gamma(x) - x\ln(x)\int x\Gamma(x) dx + \int \ln(y)\int x\Gamma(x) dx dy + \int \int y\Gamma(x) dx dy$$

$$\frac{3}{2}\int x! dx = x^2\Gamma(x) - x\ln(x)\int x\Gamma(x) dx + \int \ln(y)\int x\Gamma(x) dx dy + \int \int y\Gamma(x) dx dy$$

Because there are 2 variables now and there are also 2 integrals so we can split them:

$$\frac{3}{2}\int x! dx = x^2\Gamma(x) - x\ln(x)\int x\Gamma(x) dx + \int \ln(y) dy \int x\Gamma(x) dx + \int y dy \int \Gamma(x) dx$$

Then we solve the simple integrals over y (and also simplify all $x\Gamma(x)$ to $x!$):

$$\frac{3}{2}\int x! dx = x^2\Gamma(x) - x\ln(x)\int x! dx + (y\ln(y) - y)\int x! dx + \frac{y^2}{2}\int \Gamma(x) dx$$

$$\frac{3}{2}\int x! dx = x^2\Gamma(x) - x\ln(x)\int x! dx + y(\ln(y) - 1)\int x! dx + \frac{y^2}{2}\int \Gamma(x) dx$$

We then factor out $\int x! dx$

$$\frac{3}{2} \int x! dx = x^2 \Gamma(x) + (\int x! dx)(y \ln(y) - y - x \ln(x)) + \frac{y^2}{2} \int \Gamma(x) dx$$

Then to turn the $\int \Gamma(x) dx$ to a variation of $\int x! dx$ so we can factorize it, we multiply the insides with an $\frac{x}{x}$:

$$\frac{3}{2} \int x! dx = x^2 \Gamma(x) + (\int x! dx)(y \ln(y) - y - x \ln(x)) + \frac{y^2}{2} \int \frac{x \Gamma(x)}{x} dx$$

Then we turn the x in the denominator to a y and take it out of the integral:

$$\frac{3}{2} \int x! dx = x^2 \Gamma(x) + (\int x! dx)(y \ln(y) - y - x \ln(x)) + \frac{y^2}{2} \int \frac{x \Gamma(x)}{y} dx$$

$$\frac{3}{2} \int x! dx = x^2 \Gamma(x) + (\int x! dx)(y \ln(y) - y - x \ln(x)) + \frac{y}{2} \int x! dx$$

Then we factorize that $\int x! dx$:

$$\frac{3}{2} \int x! dx = x^2 \Gamma(x) + (\int x! dx)(y \ln(y) - y - x \ln(x) + \frac{y}{2})$$

Now we subtract that $\frac{3}{2} \int x! dx$ from both sides and factorize that integral once again:

$$0 = x^2 \Gamma(x) + (\int x! dx)(y \ln(y) - y - x \ln(x) + \frac{y}{2}) - \frac{3}{2} \int x! dx$$

$$0 = x^2 \Gamma(x) + (\int x! dx)(y \ln(y) - y - x \ln(x) + \frac{y}{2} - \frac{3}{2})$$

$$0 = x^2 \Gamma(x) + (\int x! dx)(y \ln(y) - y - x \ln(x) + \frac{y-3}{2})$$

$$0 = x^2 \Gamma(x) + (\int x! dx)(y \ln(y) - x \ln(x) + \frac{-y-3}{2})$$

$$0 = x^2 \Gamma(x) + (\int x! dx)(y \ln(y) - x \ln(x) - \frac{y+3}{2})$$

Then we move the $x^2 \Gamma(x)$ to the other side and divide $y \ln(y) - x \ln(x) - \frac{y+3}{2}$:

$$-x^2 \Gamma(x) = (\int x! dx)(y \ln(y) - x \ln(x) - \frac{y+3}{2})$$

$$-\frac{x^2 \Gamma(x)}{y \ln(y) - x \ln(x) - \frac{y+3}{2}} = \int x! dx$$

Now we just have to simplify it:

$$\int x! dx = \frac{x!x}{x \ln(x) - y \ln(y) + \frac{y+3}{2}} + C$$

Now about the variable y , you're allowed to do this because well we say that y is an **independent** variable. So we won't change y back. It's just there in the final answer. Now for the value of y in the definite integral, it's not going to be constant but instead it's going to be a multivariable function $y(a, b)$ where a and b are taken from $\int_a^b x! dx$. For now we haven't solved for the multivariable function but we have found a pretty accurate constant which is 3.36, about $y(a, b)$ it's probably not as simple as a linear function but maybe an exponential or even a sum or product.